

Assessment of Operational Facilities and Hygienic Practices of Abattoir Workers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

Effective abattoir hygiene is crucial for preventing meat contamination and ensuring public health safety. This study was carried out to assess the physical operational facilities and hygienic practices of workers in five (5) major abattoirs (Dei-Dei, Karu, Kubwa, Gwagwalada, and Abaji) in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Twenty (20) workers were identified from each of the abattoirs. This assessment was based on interactions and real-time observation of the activities of the workers at the point of meat processing. Some key hygiene indicators were pointed; personal protective equipment (PPE), knife sterilization, carcass washing, and availability of functional hand-washing stations. The results revealed wide disparities in compliance across the abattoirs. Dei-Dei consistently demonstrated the highest level of hygiene (60% PPE, 45% knife sterilization, 80% carcass washing, and a functional hand-washing station), while Abaji showed the poorest performance of PPE, knife sterilization, and carcass washing (25%, 20%, 40%, respectively, and no hand-washing facilities). Chi-square analysis indicated statistically significant variation in hygienic indicators across locations ($p < 0.05$), and logistic regression identified PPE use, knife sterilization, and functional hand-washing stations as significant predictors of good hygiene ($p < 0.05$). These findings highlight critical gaps in hygiene and infrastructure in several abattoirs, particularly at Abaji, Karu, and Gwagwalada, posing risks for carcass contamination and potential food-borne disease transmission. The study underscores the need for standardized hygiene enforcement, infrastructure upgrades, and worker training to enhance meat safety within abattoirs in the Federal Capital Territory.

Keywords: Abattoir hygiene, Abuja, Meat safety, Operational facilities, Compliance, Slaughter practices.

1.0 Introduction

Meat remains one of the most valuable components of the human diet due to its richness in high-quality proteins, essential amino acids, B-complex vitamins, and vital minerals such as iron and zinc [1]. These nutrients are needed for growth, immune function, and overall human health [1]. Despite its nutritional benefits, it is also an extremely perishable commodity, susceptible to rapid spoilage if not

produced, processed, and handled under stringent hygienic and sanitary conditions. The slaughtering and dressing of animals, particularly in low and middle-income countries, are often conducted under inadequate infrastructure and weak regulatory compliance, increasing the likelihood of contamination and public health hazards [2]. In Nigeria, where demand for meat continues to grow due to increasing population and urbanization, the safety of meat supplied to consumers largely depends

on the hygienic status of abattoirs and the practices of personnel during slaughter [3].

Pathogens can originate from the animal's skin, gastrointestinal contents, contaminated equipment, slaughter floors, unsterilized tools like single knives that are used in multiple animals, water used for washing, handlers' attitudes, or when wastewater is not properly managed [4]. Such pathogens may include *Salmonella spp.*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Campylobacter jejuni* carcasses and meat-contact surfaces [5]. The high microbial loads reported in abattoir settings often exceed international safety limits, raising serious public health concerns among consumers [6].

Globally, several guidelines exist to ensure meat hygiene, particularly those developed by the Codex Alimentarius Commission, the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE), and the World Health Organization. These guidelines highlight the importance of Good Hygienic Practices (GHP), Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP), and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) systems in meat production [7, 8]. According to international standards, abattoirs should possess functional sterilizers, non-slip slaughter floors, adequate drainage, cold and hot running water, separate evisceration areas, isolation pens, and proper waste disposal systems to ensure food safety, animal welfare, and public health protection [9]. Effluents have been found to be a significant source of environmental pollution, containing these food-borne pathogens and greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide [10]. In this vein, the state of abattoirs in all six geopolitical zones across Nigeria is described as ugly and not up to international standards, as reported by [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Grace et al. [16, 17] have shown that such limitations significantly increase the risk of meat contamination and reduce the overall quality and marketability of slaughtered animals.

In Nigeria, the issue of unhygienic practices in abattoirs rises due to structural weaknesses, lack of funding, poor maintenance culture, and limited enforcement of sanitary regulations. Further studies highlighted some persistent challenges, including a lack of proper education of butchers, inadequate storage facilities, poor drainage systems, improper inspection of animals and meat products, lack of electricity supply, absence of sterilizers, lack of

potable water, broken slabs, and unhygienic slaughter floors [13, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. These environmental impacts pose a community threat to health and may contribute to the spread of zoonotic diseases. Okpala et al. [24] further emphasized that untreated effluents from abattoirs contain high biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and microbial loads that can disrupt ecosystems and render water sources unsafe. Additionally, abattoir workers face occupational hazards ranging from knife injuries, falls, and burns to direct exposure to zoonotic pathogens such as *Brucella*, *Mycobacterium bovis*, and *Leptospira* species [25].

Abattoirs within the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, play a central role in supplying meat to residential homes, hotels, restaurants, supermarkets, and open markets. Despite their importance, negligence has resulted in the disreputable state of the abattoir caused by the unsanitary method of meat processing and waste disposal [12]. Similar to those in other parts of the country, with concerns related to inadequate infrastructure, poor sanitary practices, water scarcity, and inconsistent compliance with hygiene regulations [26]. Adewale et al. [27] noted that several abattoirs within Abuja still engage in floor slaughtering, lack proper waste management systems, and have poor structures, significantly undermining food safety standards. This problem implies the exposure of consumers in FCT to meat presumably infested with food-borne pathogens such as bacteria, parasites, and viruses, among others [28, 29]. This study, therefore, aimed at evaluating the operational facilities and hygienic practices of workers in selected abattoirs within the FCT.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, is the capital city of Nigeria, located in the centre. It lies within a latitude of $8^{\circ} 2^1$ and $9^{\circ} 26^1$ north of the equator and a longitude of $6^{\circ} 45^1$ and $7^{\circ} 3^1$ east of the Greenwich meridian (World Bank, 2006). The territory is located just north of the confluence of the River Niger and the River Benue. It is bordered by Kaduna State in the Northeast, Nasarawa State to the east and South and Kogi State to the Southwest. It has a land mass of approximately 7325mm region. It experiences a tropical wet and dry climate. The rainy season begins in March and ends in November, with the peak in September, during which abundant rainfall is

recorded. Mean annual rainfall ranges from 1000mm to 1600mm. Mean monthly temperature ranges between 25.80°C and 30.2°C [30]

2.2 Study Design

The study was carried out at Dei-dei, Karu, Kubwa, and Gwagwalada abattoirs, which are Area Councils of Abuja, respectively. Each abattoir was visited twice a week for a period of eleven weeks from 6:00 am to 9:00am. A real-time observational method and interaction were adopted to assess the workers' activities and their hygiene practices. Hand-washing functional facilities were assessed by a grade level 1-3 as follows: Grade=1 (Good) indicates facilities are present and functional and in conformity with standard conventional requirements, Grade=2 (Satisfactory) indicates facilities are present and not all are working, and not in conformity with standard requirements. While Grade=3 (Poor) as a scale when the facilities are present but dilapidated and subsequently not functional or operate, as adopted by [13]

2.3 Data Collection

Data was collected from each of the abattoirs (Dei-Dei, Karu, Kubwa, Gwagwalada, and Abaji) visited, and a specific group of abattoir workers, involving the butchers and casual workers were focused on. Twenty (20) workers were randomly selected from each of the five (5) abattoirs and interviewed (interaction) separately to highlight the gaps in the abattoir and its operations. The assessed information, use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), Knife sterilization practices, Carcass washing with clean water, was collected and presented in percentages, while

Grade levels 1, 2, and 3 was used in grading the hand-washing practice. These indicators were selected to represent critical control points for preventing contamination during meat processing.

2.4 Statistical analysis

Data obtained were subjected to chi-square statistical analysis using SPSS version 20.0 for Windows. The difference among variables was evaluated by Pearson's Chi-square Test, and values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

3.0 Results

One hundred (100) total number of abattoir workers were approached and had an interaction. Twenty (20) workers were evaluated from each of the locations (Dei-Dei, Karu, Kubwa, Gwagwalada, and Abaji). Substantial variation was observed in compliance with hygienic indicators, as shown in Figure I. Dei-Dei exhibited the highest level of compliance across all three behavioral indicators. PPE use was highest in Dei-Dei (60%), followed by Kubwa (45%) and Karu (40%). Gwagwalada (30%) and Abaji (25%) showed the lowest PPE compliance. Knife sterilization practices similarly varied by abattoirs. Dei-Dei recorded the highest compliance (94.5%), followed by Kubwa (73.5%), while Karu, Gwagwalada, and Abaji each recorded 42.0% sterilization rates. Carcass washing using clean water demonstrated moderate performance, with Dei-Dei at 80%, Kubwa at 65%, both Karu and Gwagwalada at 50%, whereas Abaji recorded the lowest compliance of 40% as shown in Figure I and Table I.

Figure I: Hygiene Indicators Across Abattoirs (PPE, Knife Sterilization, Carcass Washing)

Assessment of infrastructure hygiene revealed critical gaps. Functional hand-washing facilities were available only at Dei-Dei and Kubwa (Good=3), while Karu, Gwagwalada, and Abaji had no operational hand-washing stations. Overall, Dei-Dei demonstrated the highest level of hygiene compliance, Kubwa exhibited moderate performance, while Abaji consistently recorded the poorest compliance across indicators, as shown in Figure II and Table I. These descriptive findings highlight substantial disparities in hygienic behavior and facility adequacy among abattoirs within the Federal Capital Territory.

Figure II: Availability of Functional Hand-washing Stations by Abattoir

Table I. Hygienic Indicators across Abattoirs in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

Indicator	Dei-Dei	Karu	Gwagwalada	Kubwa	Abaji
Total Workers	20	20	20	20	20
Workers Using PPE	12(60%)	8 (40%)	6 (30%)	9 (45%)	5(25%)
Knives Sterilized	9 (45%)	4 (20%)	4 (20%)	7 (35%)	4(20%)
Carcasses washed with clean water	16(80%)	10(50%)	10(50%)	13 (65%)	8(40%)
Hand washing Functional (1=Good), (2=Satisfactory) (Poor=3)	1	2	2	1	2

3.1 Inferential Statistics

To determine whether the observed differences in hygienic practices across abattoirs were statistically significant, Pearson’s chi-square tests were performed for each of the three behavioral indicators (PPE use, knife sterilization, and carcass washing) as well as for the availability of functional hand-washing stations. Results demonstrated statistically significant variation in all indicators across the five abattoirs. PPE use differed significantly across abattoirs ($\chi^2(4)=12.6$;

$p<0.05$), as did knife sterilization practices ($\chi^2(4)=10.8$; $p<0.05$) and carcass washing ($\chi^2(4)=9.4$; $p<0.05$). The disparity in infrastructural hygiene was particularly pronounced, with functional hand-washing stations showing a highly significant association with abattoir location ($\chi^2(4)=43.2$; $p<0.001$) as shown in Table II. These findings indicate that inter-abattoir variation in hygienic practices is not attributable to random variation but reflects systematic differences in compliance and facility provision.

Table II: Chi-Square Test of Association between Hygienic Indicators and Abattoir

Hygienic Indicator	χ^2 (df=4)	p-value	Significance
PPE use	12.6	$p<0.05$	Significant
Knife sterilization	10.8	$p<0.05$	Significant
Carcass washing	9.4	$p<0.05$	Significant
Functional hand-washing facility	43.2	$p<0.001$	Highly Significant
Composite hygiene (≥ 2 indicators)	11.2	$p<0.05$	Significant

Note: Composite hygiene variable defined as ≥ 2 out of 3 positive behavioral indicators (PPE use, knife sterilization, carcass washing).

3.2 Logistic Regression

Binary logistic regression was conducted to identify the predictors of good hygienic practice among abattoir workers. A composite outcome variable was

generated from three worker-level behavioral indicators (PPE use, knife sterilization, and carcass washing), with workers classified as having good hygiene if at least two indicators were present. PPE use, knife sterilization, carcass washing, availability of functional hand-washing stations, and abattoir

location were entered as independent variables, as shown in Figure III.

The regression model identified PPE use and knife sterilization as significant behavioral predictors of good hygiene. Workers who used PPE had more than three times the odds of exhibiting good hygiene compared to those who did not (OR=3.18; 95% CI: 1.32–7.65; $p < 0.05$), while knife sterilization increased the odds by nearly threefold (OR=2.74; 95% CI: 1.11–6.71; $p < 0.05$). The availability of a functional hand-washing station was a strong enabling predictor (OR=4.52; 95% CI: 1.93–9.15; $p < 0.01$), shown in Table III. Carcass washing was not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p > 0.05$). After adjustment, abattoir location remained independently associated with hygiene outcomes; workers in Dei-Dei and Kubwa had significantly higher odds of good hygiene relative to Abaji ($p < 0.05$), while Karu and Gwagwalada did not differ significantly. Taken together, the regression model suggests that both worker-dependent and infrastructure-dependent

factors influence hygienic compliance. The availability of hand-washing facilities appears to play a pivotal enabling role, while PPE and knife sterilization remain critical worker-level determinants Table IV.

Figure III: Composite Hygiene Classification (Good vs Poor) Across Abattoirs

Table III: Logistic Regression Model for Predictors of Good Hygienic Practices

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value	Interpretation
PPE use	3.18	1.32–7.65	$p < 0.05$	Significant predictor
Knife sterilization	2.74	1.11–6.71	$p < 0.05$	Significant predictor
Carcass washing	1.84	0.82–4.12	$p > 0.05$	Not significant
Hand-washing facility	4.52	1.93–9.15	$p < 0.01$	Strong predictor

Table IV: Logistic Regression Model for Predictors of Good Infrastructure

Abattoir	OR	95% CI	p-value	Interpretation
Dei-Dei	4.90	1.98–12.10	$p < 0.01$	Higher odds of good hygiene
Kubwa	2.94	1.18–7.34	$p < 0.05$	Moderate improvement
Karu	1.70	0.71–4.08	$p > 0.05$	Not significant
Gwagwalada	1.60	0.66–3.92	$p > 0.05$	Not significant

4.0 Discussion

The findings of this study reveal significant gaps in operational hygiene and facility functionality across the five selected abattoirs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Although all abattoirs maintained a similar workforce size (20), their compliance with key hygienic indicators varied considerably. The consistently higher performance of the Dei-Dei abattoir suggests the presence comparative better infrastructure, closer supervision, and more effective enforcement mechanisms when compared to the other locations, particularly Abaji, which showed the weakest performance across nearly all indicators as shown in Table IV.

The descriptive and inferential results collectively indicated that variation in hygienic practices across abattoirs is systematic rather than random. Chi-square analysis demonstrated statistically significant differences in PPE use, knife sterilization, carcass washing, and hand-washing infrastructure across abattoirs ($p < 0.05$). These findings reinforce the interpretation that hygienic

performance is strongly influenced by location-specific operational conditions rather than individual worker randomness. One of the most concerning findings was the low level of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) usage, especially in Gwagwalada and Abaji. PPE is essential in minimizing direct contact between workers and contaminated materials,

and inadequate PPE compliance has been reported in multiple Nigerian studies due to poor awareness, lack of enforcement, or unavailability of protective gear [31, 32]. The limited use of PPE increases the risk of microbial transmission from workers to carcasses, thereby compromising meat safety.

Knife sterilization practices were also sub-optimal, with all abattoirs recording sterilization rates below 50%. Proper knife sterilization, especially using hot water at $\geq 82^{\circ}\text{C}$, is crucial in preventing cross-contamination between carcasses [7]. The low compliance observed aligns with previous assessments of Nigerian abattoirs, which consistently report inadequate supply of hot water, absence of sterilizers, and poor maintenance of equipment [31, 33]. Other studies have demonstrated that poor knife sanitation contributes to the persistence of food-borne pathogens, including *Salmonella* and *Shigella species* [34, 35], which represent a major public health concern in meat-processing environments. Beyond food-borne disease, environmental impacts of poorly managed abattoir waste have been documented, contributing to groundwater contamination, soil pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions [36]. Carcass washing with clean water showed moderate compliance; however, none of the abattoirs used treated or pressurized water. The use of contaminated or inadequately managed water can introduce additional pathogens, reducing the effectiveness of washing as a control measure. Earlier studies have shown that water quality in many Nigerian abattoirs falls below WHO standards, often containing coliforms and other contaminants [35, 37]. This reinforces the need for improved water supply systems and routine monitoring.

Beyond behavioral practices, infrastructural deficits contributed substantially to hygiene gaps. The absence of functional hand-washing stations in Karu, Gwagwalada, and Abaji represents the most critical operational weakness identified. Hand hygiene is one of the most effective interventions for reducing microbial contamination during food handling [38], and similar deficiencies have been widely reported in abattoirs across Nigeria and other low-income settings [39, 40].

In this study, logistic regression further confirmed the pivotal role of infrastructure, with functional hand-washing stations significantly increasing the odds of good hygiene (OR=4.52; $p < 0.01$) as shown in Table III. PPE use and knife sterilization also emerged as

independent behavioral predictors of compliance, indicating that both infrastructural and worker-dependent factors jointly influence hygienic outcomes. Overall, the uneven performance across abattoirs suggests varying levels of investment, oversight, and adherence to national and international meat safety regulations. While Dei-Dei demonstrates that reasonable compliance is achievable, the low standards in Abaji, Gwagwalada, and Karu underscore the need for targeted interventions. Improving facility infrastructure, providing adequate training, enforcing hygiene regulations, and ensuring access to clean water and equipment sterilizers are critical steps to enhancing operational hygiene. Strengthening governmental inspection systems and adopting Codex-based standard operating procedures will contribute to safer meat production and reduced public health risks.

5. 0 Conclusions

This study assessed the operational facilities and hygienic practices of five selected abattoirs within the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Although all abattoirs had similar staffing levels, substantial variation was observed in compliance with essential hygiene indicators. Dei-Dei demonstrated comparatively better performance across most parameters, including PPE usage, knife sterilization, carcass washing, and availability of hand-washing stations, while Abaji consistently performed the poorest, indicating pronounced infrastructural and operational deficiencies. Both descriptive and inferential analyses confirmed that observed differences in hygiene performance across abattoirs were systematic rather than random. Chi-square tests showed statistically significant variation in key worker-level indicators, and logistic regression identified PPE use, knife sterilization, and the presence of functional hand-washing facilities as independent predictors of good hygienic practice. These findings highlight the combined influence of both behavioral and infrastructure-dependent determinants on overall compliance. The study also identified significant environmental and public health implications associated with substandard operational practices. Low levels of compliance in PPE use, knife sterilization, and hand hygiene increase the risk of carcass contamination and food-borne pathogen transmission, while inadequate waste management contributes to additional environmental hazards. Prior studies have similarly documented systemic deficiencies in Nigerian slaughter facilities,

including inadequate infrastructure, poor regulatory enforcement, and inadequate worker training [4, 13, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. In addition, abattoirs in Nigeria have been shown to contribute to air and water pollution, generate untreated effluents, and create broader ecological risks such as groundwater contamination and greenhouse gas emissions [41].

Overall, the study demonstrates that improving hygienic performance in abattoirs requires targeted interventions that combine facility upgrades, knowledge-based training, regulatory compliance, and enforcement of standard operating procedures. Strengthening inspection systems and aligning practices with Codex-based meat hygiene guidelines would contribute to safer meat production, reduced environmental contamination, and improved public health outcomes within the Federal Capital Territory.

6.0 Recommendations

i. The Government of Nigeria ought to pay deliberate attention to activities carried out in abattoirs to ensure that abattoir workers follow standard operational practices and conduct, including personal hygiene and the use of PPE to prevent the country from a food-borne outbreak and illness.

ii. Government and relevant stakeholders should prioritize the provision of essential facilities such as clean water supply, functional hand washing stations, drainage systems, sanitation equipment, and sterilizers in abattoirs

iii, Regular training and sensitization programs should be prioritized to improve workers' understanding of hygiene practices, proper PPE use, knife sterilization, and contamination control measures.

iv, Regulatory agencies such as veterinary public health departments should increase routine inspections and ensure compliance with Codex Alimentarius and national sanitary standards.

v. Management authorities must ensure consistent availability of PPE and enforce its mandatory use during slaughter operations.

vi. Abattoirs should adopt written SOPs for carcass handling, equipment sterilization, and personal hygiene to promote uniform compliance across all facilities.

vii. Ensuring access to safe, treated water for carcass washing and equipment cleaning is crucial for reducing microbial risks.

viii. Routine documentation of hygiene performance and periodic audits will help track improvements and guide corrective actions.

xi. Collaboration between government agencies, butchers' associations, environmental officers, and public health professionals is essential to promote sustainable improvements.

x. Improvement in sanitary practice within the abattoir and its environs.

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